

Physicochemical Investigation on some Mixed-ligand Complexes of Dioxouranium(II)

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Mixed-ligand complex studies of UO_2^{II} using nitrilotriacetic acid, ethylenediamine- N,N' -diacetic acid and iminodiacetic acid as primary ligands and kojic acid picolinic acid and nitroso-R-salt as secondary ligands have been carried out potentiometrically at three different temperatures, viz. 5, 25 and 45° and $\mu=0.2 M$ (KNO_3). The thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been evaluated. The ΔG and ΔH values have been further separated into their electrostatic components ΔG_e , ΔH_e and cratic components ΔG_c , ΔH_c . The results are correlated on the basis of steric and structural characteristics of the chelates formed.

TERNARY and quaternary complexes of UO_2^{II} with various bidentate ligands have been recently studied¹⁻⁵. However, the polyamino acids have hardly been used. In all ternary complexes of UO_2^{II} reported so far, the coordination number of the central uranium atom is six (two positions being occupied by two oxygen atoms), while in quaternary complexes the coordination number attained is eight by the expansion of coordination number of uranium. The present paper reports a systematic study on ternary complexes of UO_2^{II} using tridentate iminodiacetic acid (IMDA) and tetradentate nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and ethylenediamine- N,N' -diacetic acid (EDDA) as primary ligands and bidentate kojic acid (KA), picolinic acid (PA) and nitroso-R-salt (NRS) as secondary ligands. The study has been carried out at three different temperatures, viz. 5, 25 and 45° and at $\mu=0.2 M$ KNO_3 employing modified form of Irving-Rossotti's pH-titration technique⁶. The thermodynamic parameters, namely change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been evaluated. To know the extent of covalent and ionic bonding the ΔG and ΔH values are further separated into their cratic components ΔG_c , ΔH_c and electrostatic components ΔG_e , ΔH_e .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade (B.D.H. or E. Merck). A 0.02 M uranyl nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of pure sample in known quantity of nitric acid and estimated gravimetrically⁷. The ligand solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and estimated potentiometrically. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by standard method. All experiments were carried out under inert atmosphere by bubbling nitrogen

through reaction vessel throughout the course of experiments.

ECIL expanded scale pH meter (± 0.02 pH units) with glass-calomel electrode assembly was used. To maintain a constant temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$) automatic ultracryostat MK-70 was used.

Procedure: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration of the following four mixtures (total volume 100 ml) with standard sodium hydroxide solution: (i) $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO_3 , (ii) $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ $\text{HNO}_3 + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand, (iii) $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ $\text{HNO}_3 + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ uranyl nitrate + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand, and (iv) $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ $\text{HNO}_3 + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ uranyl nitrate + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand. The ionic strength was maintained constant by adding required volume of KNO_3 solution. The ratio of metal(M) – primary ligand(A) – secondary ligand (L) was maintained at 1 : 1 : 1 in each system.

Results and Discussion

The graphs are plotted between pH and volume of sodium hydroxide solution added. The four plots obtained were, acid curve, secondary ligand curve, binary complexation curve and ternary complexation curve, respectively, for the mixtures (i) – (iv). The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants ($\log K^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$) were calculated by extended procedure of Irving and Rossotti (Table 1).

The thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been evaluated making use of temperature coefficients and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁸ and tabulated in Table 2. The ΔG and ΔH values have been further separated into their cratic

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES
 $\mu = 0.2 M (KNO_3)$

System	Constant	Temp. (°C)		
		5	25	45
KA—H	$\log K_1^H$	7.88	7.80	7.75
PA—H	$\log K_1^H$	5.32	5.20	5.10
NRS—H	$\log K_1^H$	6.90	6.78	6.75
[UO_2^{II} —IMDA—KA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{IMDA}$	7.18	6.98	6.76
[UO_2^{II} —IMDA—PA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{IMDA}$	4.68	4.52	4.34
[UO_2^{II} —IMDA—NRS]	$\log K_{MAL}^{IMDA}$	5.06	4.86	4.70
[UO_2^{II} —EDDA—KA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDDA}$	6.68	6.50	6.30
[UO_2^{II} —EDDA—PA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDDA}$	4.20	3.96	3.79
[UO_2^{II} —EDDA—NRS]	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDDA}$	5.88	5.68	5.47
[UO_2^{II} —NTA—KA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	7.21	7.03	6.80
[UO_2^{II} —NTA—PA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.64	4.42	4.22
[UO_2^{II} —NTA—NRS]	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	5.18	4.99	4.92

The formation of mixed—ligand complex is evident from (i) horizontal distance $[V_4 - V_3] - (V_2 - V_1)$ which increases till \bar{n} value reaches ~ 0.8 where pL values systematically decrease, (ii) increase in pH of precipitation from ~ 6.0 to ~ 6.6 for [UO_2^{II} —NTA—L] and [UO_2^{II} —IMDA—L], where L is the secondary ligand, and for [UO_2^{II} —EDDA—L] from pH ~ 6.5 to ~ 7.5 . Stepwise formation is evident from the fact that the horizontal distance $[(V_4 - V_3) - (V_2 - V_1)]$ is negligible in pH range of formation of primary complex indicating non-involvement of secondary ligands in the pH region of formation of primary complex.

The formation of mixed—ligand complex is favoured by the positive values of entropy. The negative values of ΔH indicate exothermic nature of the reaction while the negative values of ΔG indicate its spontaneity. The values of cratic components are more negative than the values of electrostatic components in almost all cases, indicating more participation of covalent forces than electrostatic forces.

The work leads to the conclusion that the mixed—ligand complex formation in case of [UO_2^{II} —

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

System	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta Ge$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta He$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta Gc$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta Hc$ kcal mol ⁻¹
[UO_2^{II} —IMDA—KA]	9.5	4.1	18.0	5.6	2.0	6.2	2.1
[UO_2^{II} —IMDA—PA]	6.1	3.4	9.0	3.7	1.4	4.7	2.1
[UO_2^{II} —IMDA—NRS]	6.6	3.5	10.0	4.0	1.5	4.9	2.1
[UO_2^{II} —EDDA—KA]	8.8	3.6	17.0	5.5	2.0	5.6	1.7
[UO_2^{II} —EDDA—PA]	5.4	3.7	6.0	3.0	1.1	4.8	2.7
[UO_2^{II} —EDDA—NRS]	7.7	3.6	14.0	4.7	1.7	5.4	1.9
[UO_2^{II} —NTA—KA]	9.4	4.3	17.0	5.5	2.0	6.3	2.3
[UO_2^{II} —NTA—PA]	6.0	4.7	4.0	2.6	1.0	5.7	3.8
[UO_2^{II} —NTA—NRS]	6.8	1.8	17.0	5.4	2.0	3.8	-0.1

components ΔGc and ΔHc and electrostatic components ΔGe and ΔHe by the method of Nancollas⁹. The final forms of the equations used to find out ΔGe , ΔHe , ΔGc and ΔHc are

$$\Delta Ge = -\nu(\Delta S + \Delta nR \ln 55.5) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta He = (T - \nu)(\Delta S + \Delta nR \ln 55.5) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta Gc = \Delta G - \Delta Ge - \Delta nRT \ln 55.5 \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta Hc = (\Delta H - \Delta He) \quad (4)$$

where, ν is temperature characteristics of the solvent (219° for water) and T is 298 K.

The primary complexes with NTA and IMDA start forming at pH ~ 2.0 and the formation is completed at pH ~ 3.2 . The primary complex formation with EDDA starts at pH ~ 2.6 and is completed at pH ~ 3.8 . The mixed—ligand complex formations with [UO_2^{II} —IMDA] and [UO_2^{II} —NTA] take place between pH ~ 3.2 to ~ 5.6 , while with [UO_2^{II} —EDDA] between pH ~ 3.8 to ~ 6.0 .

IMDA—L] expands the coordination number of the central uranium atom to seven, while in formations of [UO_2^{II} —EDDA—L] and [UO_2^{II} —NTA—L] the coordination number expands to eight. The stability of the complex is governed by (i) basicity of the ligand, (ii) size of the chelate ring formed and (iii) chelating characteristics of the ligand. When basicities of the three secondary ligands are compared, KA is found to form more stable complexes which may be because both the donor atoms are oxygen, while PA and NRS have one oxygen and another nitrogen donor atom. Comparatively, lower stability of NRS complex may be due to bulkier group participating in the complex formation.

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